
DIGITIZATION OF LIBRARIES EFFECT ON READERS AND THEIR READING HABBITTS

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Abstract:

Digitization is the process of converting the documents into digital format. It is and helps in early storage, transmissions and communication of information stored. In recent year's digitization of libraries have gained vast popularity as it gives information any time anywhere and also requires very less space; we may say rich information in less space. Digitization has also helped scholars for R & D as they get access to scholarly information. Digital libraries are organized source of information's. They are collection of books, letters, diaries, manuscripts, etc; Digitization of libraries is made for creating, managing and hosting the information which is digitized. Reading as the basic requirement for the gathered / stored information is most important factor. Reading means acquisition of language, communication of sharing of information and ideas. Reading is a prose of analyzing, understanding, and deriving meaning and comprehending the thoughts. This article highlights the identification of matter to be digitized, planning, selection of data, copyrights, etc, and understanding the digitization of libraries on basic of readers & reading habits.

Keywords: Digital libraries, Digitization, Reading Habits, Readers, Library Digitization procedure, Software Analog Collections. Knowledge Resource Centers (KRC)

Introduction:

Digitization is the processes of converting text pictures sound, printed material, manuscripts in the format which can be proceed by a computer. They are converted into electronic format which can be accented and made available using latest technologies such as computers, laptops, smart phones, tablets, etc as libraries are termed as knowledge Resource centers, which clearly identifies that vast Resource have been accumulated and stored which is made available to the reader whenever required.

Knowledge is and will be continuously required. Knowledge has been continuously transferred from one

generation to another generation. Many efforts have been taken by the generations together to transfer the knowledge may it be related to Mythology , history science, literature, etc., every generation has developed its own transfer methodology so as it can be made available for the coming generations. Stone tablets to oil painting to pigments in paper to books to photographic films to magnetic records to disk to optical disk. Every time the methodology of transferring the information is scientifically evolved.

Nowadays increased access to internet through mailing services, online display of data, display of information etc;

is giving timely, accurate relevant and current information to the asters. Internet computer teaching has also gained rapid acceptance throughout. We have all personally used libraries to gain inspirations spiritual, social and academic knowledge, and we all have done through reading many personalities who have kept a mark on society and the world at large were rigorous readers and used the library services for growing their own intellectuality and further contributions and present evaluations are made available by the libraries now termed as Knowledge Resource Centers.

Providing good literature, value-based education materials, out come based knowledge materials are the basics of a good library and making them all available to the potential reader is the primary responsibility of a librarian, making all these things possible will be the important contribution of KRC and the librarian by having a greater share in mounding and building a happier individual and a better society. The use of digital library will make the functions of library easier, more efficient, faster, broader inscape as compared to conventional libraries.

Library-KRC has no value if it cannot impart a substance to the learner to get educated. Educational development and a substance to education through providing apt material are two inseparable concepts; one perishes if separated by another.

In this paper, an effort is made to place the importance of library -KRC, digitization of library -KRC, Development of education through assistance to readers and attracting readers by developing reading habits.

Conceptual Framework:

Purpose of digitization

These are two main objectives of digitization

- i) Preservation of existing knowledge resources for future generation.
- ii) Providing access to the preserved resources.

Preservation through Digitization:

Information's preserved by Wikipedia org , we can get the information related to the wrath of nature and humans on libraries and sources of knowledge, for instance history clearly mentions that the most renowned repository of Buddhist knowledge – Nalanda University was burned in the year 1193 which contained 9 million manuscripts having roots of knowledge ,Buddhism and Ayurveda. The past history of the world relating to destruction of knowledge is very painful and disturbing. More than 85 great libraries of ancient past to present have faced destruction. The recent destruction caused was in 2015 which contained 8000 books rare and old manuscripts from 18th century which happened in Iraq.

Any kind of loss to knowledge resource is the great loss to the present generation of mankind and coming generations. The survival of any kind of life is depended upon the survival of the knowledge and the resources imparting knowledge. The complete ecosystems of our mother nature earth in itself is the source of knowledge and all the discoveries and inventions made by human being right from the beginning carry importance which cannot be measured and explained in words. Information requires safety and also requires retrieval whenever necessary. A student entering into Engineering, Medical, and Law, Humanities Discipline will require the knowledge of that chosen discipline as

well as information related to the discipline which will further help him to establish self in the society and the same is done by KRC's.

Through digitization the knowledge and information will be preserved which will provide integrated access to the available source in digital format which can be governed and available source in digital format which can be governed and controlled and made available according to the user group digitization has potential for qualitative of information and the quality remains the same inspire of multiple usage.

Same information can be accessed by multiple users at the same time which is termed as multiple referencing. Through digitization user can get wide area of access through multiple windows of networking and can be retrieved as per requirements which saves time of the user and user also is benefited at the time when required. Archival storage, security, linkage to database is all benefits of preservation of knowledge resource and information.

Through identifying the requirements importance of the source of knowledge and the contribution of the source to the society through conducting survey and identifying the interest of user for specific collection, the librarian can preserve the data for the user groups.

Before entering into digitization, librarian personnel of the knowledge resource shall analyze some following parameters for digitization

- Identify the requirement
- Conducting survey of requirement
- Considering technical factors which are available,
- Planning and consulting costs,

- Salary and training cost for manpower involved in digitization ,
- Digitization cost
- Quality check cost.

After completing all the necessary activities and responsibilities, the most important factor for which all the efforts are taken is the Reader and to provide access to the Preserved Resources.

Providing Access through Preserved Resources:

All the preserved data is to be provided to the user through an access point is the important task of the Librarian or the personnel of the Knowledge Resource. The data nowadays is made available through search engines, for example – Google, DuckDuckGo, Bing, Wiki, Twitter, Internet Archive, etc., The Librarian or the personnel of the Knowledge Resource by following certain procedure can provide the access, he has to

- Treat the users as customers,
- Enable continuous innovation,
- Try to make things better, faster, cheaper, and more convenient,
- Making data more personalized for users.
- Expedite the systematic development of procedure to collect, store and organize the information form.
- Encourage co-operative efforts in research resource, computing, and communication networks.

Through making the preserved data available and accessible will provide the platform for E-Learning and E-Reading and will overcome the problem of the getting access to the User Groups at large.

Readers and Their Reading Habits:

Reading (Cunningham, 2001) is done in initial stage for decoding, word

recognition and comprehension. Reading has been an intellectual activity and has created a clear differentiation between literate and illiterate. Reading has different effects on different stages of Life, and hence reading varies. At college level it is part of academic requirements, during Research it is the part of generating of new knowledge and ideas. In knowledge world, people reading are in pursuit of getting excellence and for persons who read out of compulsions are habitual readers. So at all the stages of an individual – Child, Adolescent or Adult, reading varies and the habits accordingly vary too.

As the format of available information has been changing according to changing time and technology, the reading habits of the human beings have also changed. The basic objective of reading was to acquire knowledge and evolve and again transfer the gained knowledge from one generation to another. The published paperback books had the danger of decay, destruction, chemical changes, paper quality and life, wrong treatment of paper. And hence, Digitization has its importance as all data of past historians to the future generations of the art, science, news, and all other records when digitized, we can outlast even for our own life times.

A common mans perception towards hard bound books is that they give a feeling of being good, they are preferred when one really need to concentrate, underlining the important sentences, creating notes after reading, etc have certain impact on the intellect of the individual and has deep advantages on the readers life. Arrival of Internet, Kindle, Smartphone's, Tablets, etc has proved benefactors to them who are unable to go the Libraries, zoom in option has helped

those groups who have vision difficulties such as patients having medical problems, old aged peoples, etc., whereas the 70-80% mass group of young readers have switched the other part of Internet such as, Social Media having – Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, Snap Chat, Online Games, etc., which have taken away the larger group away from Reading. The Librarians have to be well learned and well updated to face these groups when creating a readers group and has to be much creative to tackle the needs of the young readers.

Possible Solutions and Conclusion:

Through careful management of digitization activities and indentifying the areas of structured service the digital library will provide quality services to the users and to the organization. The Librarian or the Personnel of Knowledge Resource Center shall be well versed with all technologies available and treat the users as customers and even he should use the techniques of Management Studies such as Customer (Reader) Satisfaction, Market Survey, Customer (Reader) Demand, Changing Market Trends for Customers (Reader), etc., and learn new techniques to attract the users / readers. Through becoming well versed with the available resources the Librarian or the Personnel of Knowledge Resource Center can give a proper justice to Digitization, Reader and develop Reading Habits.

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